

INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE PELVIC ORGANS: MODERN ASPECTS OF TACTICS

Olimova Nasiba Ismatullayevna

PhD., Dean of the Clinical faculty

Asia International University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan

Email: nasibaolimova89@gmail.com

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Abstract: The review presents data on the epidemiology, etiology, features of the clinical course and diagnosis of inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs in women, and analyzes risk factors for inflammatory diseases in women. Modern aspects of tactics for inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs are considered. The role of consciously lowering the diagnostic threshold for inflammatory diseases and the prescription of empirical, antimicrobial therapy aimed at the greatest coverage of possible microbial pathogens is emphasized. Conditions that make it difficult to choose optimal treatment with antimicrobial drugs are presented. Thus, inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs remain one of the pressing problems of modern gynecology, the solution of which should be aimed at prevention and increasing the reproductive potential of women who have previously suffered from this pathology.

Key words: pelvic inflammatory diseases, gram-negative bacteria, gram-positive cocci, representatives of the class Mollicutes, sensitivity of microflora to antimicrobial drugs, infertility, miscarriage.

Pelvic inflammatory diseases (PID) are among the most widespread diseases in modern gynecology. PID has a significant negative impact on morbidity, quality of life, and reproductive health of women.¹ In Russia, patients with PID make up 60-65% of the total number of patients who applied to the antenatal clinic, and 30% of patients sent to the hospital. According to the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare of the Russian Federation, the frequency of salpingitis and oophoritis in Russia is 1,236.7 per 100,000 female populations (2020), the value of the same indicator in the Far Eastern Federal District (FEFD) was 1,306.9 per 100,000 female population (2020).

In the United States, up to 1 million new cases of PID are diagnosed annually. This pathology affects up to 2% of sexually active women under the age of 25. The peak incidence occurs at the age of 17-28 years, and is clearly comparable to an active sexual life and the absence of barrier methods of contraception. PID accounts for approximately 2.5 million visits to physicians, despite the fact that only 11% of women with PID in the United States receive hospital treatment. The financial cost of treating PID in the United States is \$4 billion per year. The main costs, in this regard, are due to the treatment of complications of PID such as infertility, chronic pelvic pain, ectopic pregnancy.² The frequency of female infertility in the

¹ Гинекология: национальное руководство / Под ред. В.И. Кулакова, И.Б. Манухина, Г.М. Савельевой. - М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2007. - 1072 с. // Неотложные состояния в акушерстве: Руководство для врачей / В.Н. Серов [и др.]. М. : ГЭОТАР-Ме-диа, 2010. - 320 с.

² Jernberg E., Mogbaddam A., Moi H. Azithromycini and maxifloxacin for microbiological cure of Mycoplasma genitalium infection: an open study. Int J STD AIDS 2008; 19: 676-9.

Russian Federation remains quite high and amounts to 517.5 per 100,000 female population (2010), this figure in the Far Eastern Federal District is 385.6 per 100,000 female population. In addition, the frequency of ectopic pregnancy in the Russian Federation in the structure of causes of maternal mortality reaches 3%, and in the Far Eastern Federal District, in some years this figure reaches 6-7%.

The incidence of complications increases with the number of episodes of the disease. After the first episode of PID, infertility develops in 15% of women, and chronic pelvic pain and ectopic pregnancy in 10% of patients. In women who have had two episodes of the disease, the incidence of chronic pelvic pain increases to 30%, and in women who have had three or more episodes - up to 67%. Repeated episodes of PID are associated with a 4- to 6-fold increase in the risk of irreversible fallopian tube damage [11, 18, 22, 40].

Despite the special attention paid to this problem, success in the prevention of reproductive complications of PID has not been achieved [22, 41]. The main trigger for the development of PID is microbial invasion. The cervix represents an important protective barrier against the spread of bacteria into the internal genital organs. The presence of pathogenic bacteria in the cervical canal may indicate both its contamination and true colonization. An unambiguous interpretation is difficult due to the lack of such a concept as normal cervical flora [10].

Многие авторы единодушны во мнении, что ведущим инициатором ВЗОМТ являются *Chlamydia trachomatis* (30 %), *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* (50 %), в то же время представители нормальной флоры полового тракта (анаэробы, *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Neamophilus influenzae*, *Streptococcus agalactiae*, *E.coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus* и т.д.) играют важную роль в поддержании воспалительного процесса [10, 18, 19, 24, 25, 35]. В настоящее время с ВЗОМТ стали ассоциировать цитомегаловирус, представителей класса Mollicutes (*Mycoplasma genitalium*, *Ureaplasma urealiticum*, *Mycoplasma hominis*). По мнению ряда авторов *Mycoplasma hominis* в 15-30 % случаев является причиной ВЗОМТ. Важно отметить, что в 15-20 % случаев ВЗОМТ возбудитель выявить не удастся [3, 5, 6, 26, 28].

According to a number of researchers, one of the pressing problems is to determine the degree of influence of representatives of the class Mollicutes on reproductive function. Infertility in women can be a consequence of inflammatory processes in the urogenital tract caused by ureaplasma infection (UMI). Morphological and functional changes in the organs of the reproductive system during PID and UMI cause pathological afferentation in the parts of the central nervous system that regulate the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian system. As a result of these changes, there is a decrease in the endocrine function of the ovaries, leading to disruption of the ovulation process. Inflammatory processes in the endometrium lead to its structural and functional inferiority, disruption of the receptor apparatus, which, in turn, causes premature termination of pregnancy.

Reports have been published on the ability of mycoplasmas to cause chromosomal changes in cells, affecting the chromosomal apparatus of diploid cells of the human embryo. The changes in cells caused by *Mycoplasma hominis* were similar to those caused by Down's disease. The appearance of chromosomal aberrations was noted in human leukocytes during infection with *Ureaplasma urealiticum*, isolated from women with recurrent miscarriage. It is

known that ureaplasma is adsorbed on sperm and is found in women with spontaneous abortions.³

In all variants of mycoplasma and mixed infection, women with a burdened obstetric history experienced vascular, dystrophic, necrotic and proliferative changes in the placenta, which led to circulatory disturbances in the “mother-placenta-fetus” system. A characteristic complication of pregnancy with infections caused by mycoplasmas is the formation of chronic placental insufficiency and fetal malformations (kidney dysplasia, subsequently leading to the development of pyelonephritis). In almost all cases, pregnancy in women infected with mycoplasmas is complicated by the threat of miscarriage, gestosis, intrauterine infection, and premature rupture of membranes. The outcome of such pregnancies is miscarriage.

PID refers to the entire spectrum of inflammatory processes in the upper reproductive tract of women. They can be represented by one nosological form (endometritis, salpingitis, oophoritis, tubo-ovarian abscess, pelvioperitonitis), or any combination thereof.

Routes of infection include:

- ascending - through the cervical canal, uterine cavity, fallopian tubes - to the pelvic peritoneum and abdominal organs, including during various medical procedures (instrumental abortion and uterine curettage, insertion of intrauterine contraceptives (IUD), hysterosalngoscopy, etc. .d.);
- lymphogenous;
- hematogenous;
- contact - along the peritoneum, from the primary pathological focus of the abdominal organs, for example, with appendicitis.

The clinical picture of PID is extremely variable, and even an acute inflammatory process can cause certain difficulties in diagnosis due to the large number of possible symptoms. A significant proportion are patients with a mild or subclinical course of the disease. At the same time, delayed diagnosis and treatment contribute to the spread of the inflammatory process to the upper parts of the reproductive tract.

When diagnosing PID, it is important to identify risk groups:

- a history of STIs and previous episodes of PID;
- surgical intervention on the organs of the reproductive system, especially intrauterine manipulation;
- a history of complications of the gestational period and childbirth;
- long-term use of an IUD;
- frequent change of sexual partners and lack of barrier methods of contraception.⁴

Clinical diagnosis of acute PID is often inaccurate and has a 65-90% predictive value compared to laparoscopy. The number of undiagnosed cases of PID with nonspecific symptoms remains quite high. Given the difficulties of diagnosis and the potential risk for reproductive health (even in cases of atypical and asymptomatic course), many clinicians consider it advisable to significantly lower the diagnostic threshold for PID.

³ Кузьмин В.Н., Гусейнзаде М.И. Современные представления о роли микоплазменной инфекции в структуре воспалительных заболеваний органов малого таза // Consilium medicum. - № 6 - Т. 13. - 2011. - С. 40-45.

⁴ Boek A.J. The risk of pelvic inflammatory disease with urogenital infection with Chlamydia trachomatis. Ned Tijdschr Geneesk 2005; 16 (149): 878-884.

According to a number of researchers, therapy for PID should be reasonably aggressive and based primarily on empirical antimicrobial therapy with drugs with a broad spectrum of action. A prerequisite for therapy is the effectiveness of antibiotics against *Neisseria gonorrhoeae* and *Chlamydia trachomatis*, even in the case of negative results of bacterioscopic, bacteriological examination, polymerase chain reaction method of material from the cervical canal, since the possibility of the presence of these microorganisms in the overlying parts of the female genital organs cannot be excluded.

The main component of treatment for PID is antibiotics. Solving the issue of adequacy and timeliness of antibacterial therapy is the most pressing and is often life-sustaining.⁵

The complexity of resolving this issue is due to a number of conditions:

- variety of etiologically significant pathogens (mixed infections) of PID;
- the need to use broad-spectrum antibiotics or, more often, a combination of antibiotics;
- empiricism of initial therapy;
- frequent irrational use of antibiotics and the resulting increase in resistance to pathogens.⁶

Currently, medical communities offer different treatment regimens for PID, and although the same groups of antibacterial drugs are used, differences in doses, regimens and combinations of drugs are allowed. In a hospital setting, intravenous administration of drugs should continue for at least 24 hours after the onset of symptoms of clinical improvement, and then the patient should be transferred to an oral regimen of drugs. The absence of positive clinical dynamics within 72 hours, while taking antimicrobial therapy, in severe PID is an indication for surgical exploration of the abdominal organs. In all inpatient and outpatient treatment regimens, metronidazole-containing drugs must be used.

The variety of modern antibiotics provides sufficient opportunities for their choice, however, adequate therapy should be based primarily on the effectiveness and safety of antibiotics proven in controlled clinical trials and, of course, data on their resistance. Thus, modern tactics for PID should include a modern algorithm of diagnostic and treatment resources, a conscious reduction in the diagnostic threshold, the use of empirically selected combinations of antimicrobial drugs, as well as prediction of possible complications and outcomes of the disease.

⁵ Jaiyeoba O., Lazenby G., Soper D.E. Recommendations and rationale for the treatment of inflammatory disease. *Expert Rev Anti Infect Ther* 2011; 9 (1): 61-70.

⁶ Рациональная фармакотерапия в акушерстве и гинекологии: Рук. Для практикующих врачей / В.И. Кулаков, В.Н. Серов, П.Р. Абакарова и др. - М.: Литтерра, 2005. - 1152 с.

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